

A Vector Error Correction Model (Vecm) An Approach To Short-Run And Long-Run Causality Between Solvency And Liquidity: A Study Of Oil & Gas Development Company Limited (Ogdcl), Pakistan

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ABSTRACT

The aim of the research was to examine the short-run and long-run causality between solvency and liquidity in case of Oil and Gas Development Company Limited (OGDCL), Pakistan. The secondary data of 26 years was employed from 1990 to 2015 to evaluate the results. The series of two separate regressions were run to check causality separately. Out of 9 hypotheses, 4 were rejected and 5 were accepted. Vector Error Correction Model (VECM), Cointegration and Wald test were used as statistical tools. The results concluded that Current Ratio (CR) has no long-run association with Debt to Equity (DTE) and Debt to Assets (DTA), but Quick Ratio (QR) is having long-run association with Debt to Equity (DTE) and Debt to Assets (DTA). Moreover, Current Ratio (CR) has short-run association with Debt to Assets (DTA). Similarly, Quick Ratio (QR) is having no short-run association with Debt to Equity (DTE).

Keywords: *Oil and Gas Development Company Limited, Current Ratio, Quick Ratio, Debt to Equity, Debt to Assets.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Liquidity measures how quickly a company can meet its short term financial obligations with the liquid assets available. Solvency means the company's ability and capability to meet its long term financial obligation, *Yadav (2014)*. For every firm strong liquidity position is very essential. Most often liquidity is measured with the help of three ratios i.e. (Current Ratio, Quick Ratio & Absolutely Liquidity Ratio). Liquid assets usually generate less profit than fixed profit, *Vieira, (2010)*. The concept of liquidity is receiving grave attention day by day in terms of recent financial scenarios and the world economy, *Sunday and Small (2012)*. The business managers and decision makers have the great concern to develop a suitable plan to overcome the obligation and increase the profitability. A firm needs to ensure that they have sufficient funds to meet their short-term obligations. Liquidity is a technique to increase funds; if a firm is unable to meet its short-term obligations, the firm may face liquidity risk. Alternatively, an effective liquidity measures could emerge a strong position of a company, *Kumar & Yadav (2013)*.

The Oil and Gas companies and energy companies working in Pakistan has recently been facing some liquidity and solvency problems due non-payment of outstanding bills and receipts that need to be paid by the consumers. This non-payment of outstanding dues may lead the companies or firms into circular debt. Therefore, it is very important to investigate the short-run and long-run causality/association between solvency and liquidity to examine how they move in short-run and long-run.

It is assumed that more or less Oil and Gas Development Company Limited (OGDCL), Pakistan might face some liquidity and solvency issues in future. Moreover, it is assumed that the company has long-run and short-run association and causality with solvency and liquidity.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The term “liquidity” is having great significance for every organization in a way that it pays current obligations, *Khidmat and Rehman (2014)*. Nine years of data set from 10 chemical sector companies were taken for data analysis. The result indicated that solvency ratio had negative impact on Return on Assets (ROA) and Return on Equity (ROE). Moreover, the performance will decrease, if debt to equity ratio increases. The research concluded that liquidity has significant positive impact on Return on Assets (ROA).

Return on Assets (ROA) and Return on Equity (ROE) were used dependent variables and Current Ratio (CR), Quick Ratio (QR), Debt to Equity Ratio (DE) and Interest Coverage Ratio (ICR) were used independent variables.

Paswan (2013) in his research paper examined that solvency of liquidity is important because it provides the external & internal users such as creditors, investors and suppliers the information about the company and it indicates how quickly the companies are capable enough to pay their short term obligations before making any investment. The annual data from 2005-2006 to 2010-2011 of six selected FMCG companies in India was collected. Standard Deviation and Co-efficient of variation was the statistical tools used. The result indicated high debt equity ratio of *Emani and Dabur*. The research concluded that assets of the company are financed by debt. *Munteanu.I (2012)*, in his research discussed that most of the profitable banks encountered several difficulties in managing their funds because of mishandling of liquidity risk. The panel of commercial banks in Romania along with multiple regression model was taken on board to analyze the results. The data set from 2002-2007 of various commercial banks in Romania was taken as a sample. Results indicated that Z-Score had a significant impact on bank liquidity in the crisis year. The research concluded observance of pre-crisis period 2008-2010. The reductions in liquidity creation can inimical economic growth, *Weill, Seidler and Horvath, (2012)*. Granger-Causality test was used as a statistical tool with the help of panel data. The data set from 2000 to 2010 was taken as sample. The study resulted that capital was negatively granger-cause to liquidity creation. The research also concluded that there is trade-off between financial stability and capital requirement. The liquidity, profitability and solvency are the factors which cause unstable financial position and inadequate working capital of various small and medium enterprises (SMEs), *Nyanyuk, Simeyo and Patrick. (2013)*. The research covered the period form 2009-2011 and was extracted from financial statements of three SMEs. ANOVA and simple regression were used being statistical tools for data analysis. Results revealed that there was a significant impact of current ratio, quick ratio and debt to equity ratio. The study concluded that liquidity position of SMEs was not satisfactory and below the acceptance level. The liquidity and profitability play a vital role in financial performance analysis, *Bhunja, Mukhuti and Roy, (2011)*. The research examined the financial strength and weaknesses of Indian Public Sector Pharmaceutical enterprises. The study took two public sectors pharmaceutical enterprises with data set from 1997-98 to 2008-2009 along with multiple regression models. Financial performance of both companies reflected diminishing trends and reduction at an interest rate. The study concluded that liquidity position was strong in case of KAPL and poor in case of RDPL. Liquidity has a great influence on day to day operations of the business, *Sunday and Small (2012)*. The research measured the relationship between liquidity management and profitability. The selected data of manufacturing companies from Nigerians Stock Exchange was taken as sample. The descriptive statistics was taken on board to analyze the results. The result indicated significant impact of cash flow management and cash conversion cycles on corporate profitability. The study concluded that managers and decision makers can enhance profitability by framing decent cash flow management and credit policies. There is close relationship between liquidity and solvency of banks. The best liquidity position indicates minimum chances for the firm to become insolvent, *Kumar & Yadav (2013)*. Liquidity and solvency are two most essential factors for the survival of any firm. The comparative study of five FMCG companies from India was taken to carry out the research. The study was based on secondary data which was obtained from annual reports, *Mehrotra (2013)*. The risk of insolvency is created when the companies do not have adequate cash available to them to fulfill their short term obligation, *Ljubaj, Kunovac and Ivicic (2008)*. Solvency and liquidity strengthens the financial health of an enterprise. A solvent company is a one with having positive net worth, *Gabilondo (2014)*. A high proprietary ratio is always expected by creditors of the company, *William (2014)*. Working capital decisions are based on profitability and

liquidity implication. To achieve desirable working capital targets, a firm needs to control a tradeoff between profitability and liquidity. The liquidity plays one of the most important roles in firm success. If the firm is having weak liquidity position may be facing high risk, *Bhunia, Khan and Mukhuti (2011)*. Liquidity can be checked with current and quick ratios. Profitability of a firm can be evaluated by using net profit margin ratio, return on equity ratio and return on asset ratio. Similarly, solvency can be ascertained with the help of debt to equity ratio, fixed asset ratio and equity to total asset ratios, *Abbas and Habiba (2013)*. The firms having high liquidity may have low risk and profitability, *Niresh (2012)*. Working Capital is a healthy financial indicator, *Guimarae and Nossa (2010)*.

TABLE: 1 SEVEN COLUMN SNAPSHOT OF REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Citation	Independent Variables	Dependent Variables	Statistical Technique & Test applied	Data Set Used	Results	Conclusions of the study
<i>Khidmat and Rehman, (2014)</i>	CR, QR, DE, ICR	ROE & ROA	Regression	Nine years of data of 10 cement companies were taken	solvency ratio had negative impact on Return on Assets (ROA) and Return on Equity (ROE)	The study concluded that liquidity is having significant positive impact on Return on Assets (ROA).
<i>Paswan, (2013)</i>	Apparently not mention	Apparently not mention	Standard Deviation & Co-efficient of variance	The annual data from 2005-2006 to 2010-2011 of six selected FMCG companies	result indicated high debt equity ratio of Emani and Dabur	Assets of the company are financed by debt.
<i>Munteanu (2012)</i>	Capital Adequacy, Asset Quality, Interbank Funding, Funding Cost & Cost to Income Ratio	Liquidity	Multiple Regression Model	Panel data from 2002-2007	Z-Score has significant influence on bank liquidity	The research concluded observance of pre-crisis period (2008-2010)
<i>Weill, Seidler and Horvath, (2012)</i>	Earning Volatility, Credit Risk, Z-Score, NPL, Size, Market Share, Unemployment and Inflation.	Liquidity Creation	Granger-Causality	Panel data from 2000 to 2012	capital was negatively granger-cause to liquidity creation	there is trade-off between financial stability and capital requirement
<i>Nyanyuk, Simeyo and Patrick. (2013)</i>	Current Ratio, Quick Ratio, Debt to Total Asset, Gross Profit Margin and Net Profit Margin	Return on Assets (ROA)	ANOVA & Simple Regression	Data set from 2009-2011	there was a significant impact of current ratio, quick ratio and debt to equity ratio	Liquidity position of SMEs was not satisfactory and below the acceptance level.
<i>Bhunia, Mukhuti and Roy, (2011)</i>	Liquidity Ratio, Debt to Equity Ratio, Interest Coverage Ratio, Inventory Turnover Ratio & Debt to net worth Ratio	ROIR	Multiple Regression Model	1997-98 to 2008-2009	Financial performance of both companies reflected diminishing trends and reduction at an interest rate	Study concluded that liquidity position was strong in case of KAPL and poor in case of RDPL.

<i>Sunday and Small (2012)</i>	Days of Sales Outstanding, Days of Sales Inventory and Days of Payable outstanding	Cash Conversion Cycle (CCC)	Descriptive Statistics		Significant impact of cash flow management and cash conversion cycles on profitability.	The managers can increase profitability by devising favorable policies.
<i>Mehrotra (2013)</i>			Comparative study	Secondary data	Low liquidity ratio expose companies to face financial distress.	Most of the companies are having problems in cash flows than profitability.
<i>Ljubaj, Kunovac and Ivicic (2008)</i>	Credit growth, total assets, asset structure, credit risk, liquidity risk and inflation rate risk	Z-Score	Regression	Secondary data of 9 years from 1998-2006	Risk of insolvency in banks need to be thoroughly focused.	Z-score directly link bank insolvency risk with macroeconomic variables.
<i>William (2014)</i>			Short term & long term ratio	Secondary data 2012 – 2014 of Nestle Pvt. Ltd	Inventor turnover ratio, conversion ratio and average collection period found satisfactory.	The company liquidity position not found satisfactory.
<i>Bhunja, Khan and Mukhuti (2011)</i>	Current Ratio, Liquid Ratio, Absolute Liquid Ratio, Short-term debt equity Ratio, Age of Inventory, Age of debtor	Return on Investment Ratio	Regression and correlation	Secondary Data 1997-2006	Correlation and regression results are significantly related with firm profitability.	
<i>Abbas and Habiba (2013)</i>	Current ratio, liquidity ratio, ROA, ROE, DE Ratio	Net Profit Margin	Trend Analysis	Secondary data of five cement companies from 2005-2011	The firms have good liquidity position and reasonable solvency.	Firms had high return on assets and equity.
<i>Guimaraes and Nossa (2010)</i>	Profitability and solvency	Liquidity	ANOVA	The data of 621 health care insurance companies for the year 2006 was taken	The result indicated that financial current assets exceed current liabilities and cyclical current assets exceed cyclical current liabilities.	Financing of the company is the most essential decision for the manager.

BUILDING OF HYPOTHESES

After analyzing the previous studies, the following hypotheses are developed.

- H₁**: There is Long-run association between Current Ratio to Debt to Equity (DTE)
- H₂**: There is Long-run association between Current Ratio to Debt to Asset (DTA)
- H₃**: There is Long-run association between Quick ratio to debt to equity (DTE)
- H₄**: There is Long-run association between Quick ratio to debt to assets (DTA)
- H₅**: There is short-run association between current ratio to Debt to equity (DTE)
- H₆**: There is short-run association between Current ratio to Debt to assets (DTA)
- H₇**: There is short-run association between Quick ratio to Debt to Equity (DTE)
- H₈**: There is short-run association between Quick ratio to Debt to assets (DTA)
- H₉**: There is co-integration between variables.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Conceptual Model

Conceptual model defines theoretical framework. From the conceptual model, the following equations could be developed. The research will run the series of two regressions between dependent and independent variables separately. The following regression model has been evolved.

$$CR = \beta_0 + \beta_1 DTE + \beta_2 DTA + \varepsilon$$

Regression Equation 1

$$QR = \beta_0 + \beta_1 DTE + \beta_2 DTA + \varepsilon$$

Regression Equation 2

Where:

- CR: Current Ratio is (dependent Variable)
- QR: Quick Ratio is also (dependent variable)
- DTE: Debt to Equity is (Independent Variable)
- DTA: Debt to Asset is (Independent Variable)
- β_0 : Constant
- ε : Error Term

Sample and Data Selection

The empirical aim of this study is to evaluate the short run and long run causality between solvency and liquidity in case of Oil and Gas Development Company Limited (OGDCL), Pakistan using VEC model. The time series data of 26 years was taken into account. The secondary data for the study was taken from annual financial reports of OGDCL, Pakistan. The data was analyzed by using Eviews and hypotheses were tested at ($\alpha = 0.05$) level of significance (0.95 confidence level).

Table: 2 Variables definition and predicted relationship

Variables	Full Name	Measure	Predicted Relationship
Dependent			
CR	Current Ratio	Current Assets /Current Liabilities	
QR	Quick Ratio	Current Assets – Inventories / Current Liabilities	
Independent			
DTE	Debt to Equity	Total Debt / Total Equity	+/-
DTA	Debt to Asset	Total Debt / Total Assets	+/-

Table: 3 Hypotheses and Statistical Tools to be used

S.No	Hypotheses	Statistical Tools	Rationale for choice of the test
H ₁	There is Long-run association between Current Ratio to Debt to Equity (DTE)	Vector Error Correction Model	The Vector Error correction Model (VECM) demonstrates co-integrating relationship among the variables.
H ₂	There is Long-run association between Current Ratio to Debt to Asset (DTA)	Vector Error Correction Model	
H ₃	There is Long-run association between Quick ratio to debt to equity (DTE)	Vector Error Correction Model	
H ₄	There is Long-run association between Quick ratio to debt to assets (DTA)	Vector Error Correction Model	
H ₅	There is short-run association between current ratio to Debt to equity (DTE)	Vector Error Correction Model	
H ₆	There is short-run association between Current ratio to Debt to assets (DTA)	Vector Error Correction Model	
H ₇	There is short-run association between Quick ratio to Debt to Equity (DTE)	Vector Error Correction Model	
H ₈	There is short-run association between Quick ratio to Debt to assets (DTA)	Vector Error Correction Model	
H ₉	There is co-integration between variables.	Co-integration Test	

Stationary Test: It is a significance phenomenon because it can influence its behavior. In case x and y series are nonstationary random process the following equation generate a spurious results. *Juseof, Shamsudin., Mohamad., Jusoh, Baharuddin and Asari (2011)*. Stationary of time series data is necessary to have an effective and valid test of *t*-statistics and *F*-Statistics.

$$Y_t = \alpha + \beta X_t + \varepsilon_t$$

The stationary series without any difference is known as I (0). Similarly, stationary of first difference is labeled as I (1).

Johansen Cointegration Test: Number of cointegration vectors can be tested through Trace Statistics and Critical Value or Probability value.

Vector Error Correction Model (VECM): The Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) is an especial case of Vector Autoregressive (VAR) Model for the variables that are stationary at the first difference. The VECM can also take into the account any cointegrating relationship among variables.

4. CRITERIA FOR DEVELOPING SHORT-TERM AND LONG-TERM CAUSALITY MODEL USING VECM

We assume that all variables are integrated of same order, meaning that at level all variables are non-stationary, but when they are converted into first difference, they become stationary. By using the Johansen Cointegration test we shall check, if the variables are co-integrated or have long-run association, then we can run restricted VAR that is VECM Model. But if the variables are not co-integrated, we can not run VECM; rather we shall run unrestricted VAR.

Short run association among variables can be evaluated by applying Wald Test. If the probability values of chi-square are less than 5%, we shall reject null hypotheses and accept alternative hypotheses.

5. CRITERIA FOR DEVELOPING BEST MODEL

Test of Normality, Heteroscedasticity and serial-correlation need to be tested in order to examine the econometric modeling and indicating the best model in the research, *Gujarati (2003)*. There are three test of *Normality Test*, (1) Histogram of Residuals (2) Normal Probability Plot and (3) *Jarque Bera*.

In this research, the test of *Jarque Bera* has been employed to test whether the residuals are normally distributed. *Jarque Bera (JB)* is a test of joint hypothesis. It is especially used with large sample size. If the *p*-values are less than 5%, we shall reject null hypothesis i.e. **“Residuals are normally distributed”** or otherwise, *Gujarati (2003)*.

Heteroscedasticity means the absence of *homoscedasticity* which indicates that the error terms do not have constant variance. The presence of *heteroscedasticity* indicates a major concern in regression analysis, as it might nullify the statistical test of significance, *Gujarati (2003)*.

Serial Correlation is undesirable for the model. It happens due to dependencies within the data. In time series data when observations reflect inter-correlation, it might support autocorrelation, *Gujarati (2003)*.

6. EMPIRICAL RESULTS, FINDING AND DISCUSSION

This part of research demonstrates the detailed information on the results, findings and discussion. In this part of the research, we examine the short run and long run association between dependent and independent variables.

Table: 4 Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test Statistics

Variable	At Level	<i>t</i> -Statistics	Prob. Values	1 st Difference	<i>t</i> -Statistics	Prob. Values
CR		-1.710293	0.4141		-4.704659	0.0011
DTE		-1.580156	0.4776		-4.724733	0.0010
DTA		-1.369535	0.5798		-3.212361	0.0317
QR		-2.620481	0.1023		-5.457515	0.0002

It is recommended and pre-requisite to ensure that all variables, Current Ratio (CR), Quick Ratio (QR), Debt to Equity (DTE) and Debt to Asset (DTA) are non-stationary at level and stationary at 1st difference. ADF test was run and found that the data is non-stationary at level and stationary at 1st difference. The probability values of less than 5% indicate that all variables became stationary at 1st difference.

Table: 5 Lag Selection Criteria

Variables	Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
**CR DTA DTE	1	-74.88181	90.31505*	0.387525*	7.554940*	8.147372*	7.703935*
***QR DTE DTA	4	-46.20057	12.88945	0.787250*	7.745506*	9.679627	8.201127*

**CR DTA DTE, indicates the results of "Regression Equation 1"

*** QR DTE DTA, indicates the results of "Regression Equation 2"

Having done the ADF test, the lag selection criteria was tested and found that lag (1) will be the best choice for selection in **regression equation: 1** because in lag (1) the values of (LR, FPE, AIC, SC & HQ) are significant enough to choose lag (1). Similarly, lag (4) is the best choice to select in **regression: 2**.

Co-integration Test

Table: 6 Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Trace)

Variable(s)	Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Trace Statistics	0.05 Critical Value	Probability
**CR DTA DTE	None*	0.622850	33.36472	29.79707	0.0186
	At Most 1	0.201966	9.962003	15.49471	0.2837
	At Most 2*	0.172610	4.547498	3.841466	0.0330
***QR DTE DTA	None*	0.966105	94.71198	29.79707	0.000
	At Most 1*	0.541949	23.63775	15.49471	0.0024
	At Most 2*	0.291661	7.241486	3.841466	0.0071

**CR DTA DTE, indicates the results of "Regression Equation 1"

*** QR DTE DTA, indicates the results of "Regression Equation 2"

The probabilities values of co-integration test in **regression equation: I** indicate that there is one co-integrating equation at the 0.05 level which denotes rejection of null hypothesis. Similarly, in **regression equation: 2**, indicates that there are three co-integrating equations at the 0.05 level which denotes rejection of null hypothesis. Therefore, now we can run the VECM Model to check the long-run association.

Table: 7 Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) "Long Term Associationship"

Regression	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistics	Prob.	
*R. Equation 1	C (1)	-0.320766	0.241028	-1.330823	0.1990
	C (2)	0.121689	0.251873	0.483136	0.6345
	C (3)	-0.253685	0.139433	-1.819401	0.0846
	C (4)	-0.098500	0.162655	-0.605577	0.5520
	C (5)	0.086898	0.138715	0.626448	0.5385
**R. Equation 2	C (1)	-6.171318	1.415279	-4.360495	0.0033
	C (2)	5.078173	1.2063573	4.018898	0.0051
	C (3)	3.075911	0.876250	3.510312	0.0099
	C (4)	2.566553	0.687512	3.733105	0.0073
	C (5)	1.196508	0.478336	2.501397	0.0409
	C (6)	0.039378	0.146682	0.268462	0.7961
	C (7)	-0.051940	0.140175	-0.70538	0.7219
	C (8)	0.138115	0.160961	0.858067	0.4193
	C (9)	-0.138480	0.174761	-0.792397	0.4541
	C (10)	-2.769025	0.691413	-4.004877	0.0052
	C (11)	-2.557954	0.679087	-3.766757	0.0070
	C (12)	-1.606243	0.539941	-2.974849	0.0207
	C (13)	-1.284576	0.308541	-4.163395	0.0042
	C (14)	0.086417	0.167177	0.516921	0.6211

$$*CR = \beta_0 + \beta_1 DTE + \beta_2 DTA + \varepsilon$$

$$**QR = \beta_0 + \beta_1 DTE + \beta_2 DTA + \varepsilon$$

The result of regression **equation: 1** indicates that there is no long-run association between Current Ratio to Debt to Equity (DTE) and Debt to Assets (DTA). It means dependent variable and independent variables do not move together in long-run.

Moreover, **regression equation: 2**, shows that there is a long-run association between Quick Ratio (QR) and Debt to Equity (DTE) and Debt to Asset (DTA). It means dependent variable and independent variables move together in long-run because coefficient values (regression equation: 2) of C (1) are having negative sign and probability values are having less than 5%.

Table: 8 Wald Test “Short run Association”

Variable	t-Statistics	Value	df	Probability
CR to DTE	Chi-Square	3.310221	1	0.0689
CR to DTA	Chi-Square	0.612660	2	0.7361
QR to DTA	Chi-Square	1.579988	4	0.8124
QR to DTE	Chi-Square	33.72744	3	0.0000

The results of Current Ratio to Debt to Equity (CR to DTE) and Quick Ratio to Debt to Equity (QR to DTE) are statistically significant; hence rejection of null hypotheses, meaning that there is no short-run association between CR to DTE and QR to DTE.

Moreover, Current Ratio to Debt to Assets (CR to DTA) and Quick Ratio to Debt to Asset (QR to DTA) are statistically significant; therefore non-rejection of null hypothesis, meaning that there is a short-run association between CR to DTA and QR to DTA.

Table: 9 Serial Correlation, Heterosedasticity and Normality test

	Obs*R-squared (Prob. Chi-square)	Jarque-Bera	Prob (Values)
Serial Correlation (Breusch-Godfrey Test)	0.7264	-----	-----
Heterodasticity (Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey Test)	0.1977	-----	-----
Test of Normality	-----	7.492958	0.023601

The outcomes of *Prob. Chi-square* in serial correlation (*Breusch-Godfrey Test*) indicate that there is no autocorrelation between dependent and independent variables. Similarly, a result of Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey Test of Heterodasticity shows that there is no ARCH effect or Heterosedasticity in the data. Moreover, keeping in view, the results of *Normality Test*, it shows that residuals are normally distributed.

The significance in the outcomes of Serial Correlation, Heterosedasticity and Test of Normality indicate that the model is best fitted.

Table: 10

<i>R-squared</i>	<i>Adjusted R-squared</i>	<i>F-statistics</i>	<i>Prob.</i>
0.955	0.873	11.575	0.0016

Table No: gives us the insight that how well our overall model fits. The first measure is *R-square*. The results of *R-square* shows that there is 95.5% observed variability in dependent variable explained by independent variables. The remaining deviations are explained by some other factors which are other than the variables selected for this research or which is beyond the scope of my research. The *adjusted R-square* measures the portion of total deviation of dependent variable explained by independent variables. The probability value of 0.16% indicates the significance of the model.

Table: 11 Hypotheses Testing

<i>NO.</i>	<i>Hypotheses</i>	<i>Results</i>
<i>H₁</i>	There is Long-run association between Current Ratio to Debt to Equity (DTE)	Rejected
<i>H₂</i>	There is Long-run association between Current Ratio to Debt to Asset (DTA)	Rejected
<i>H₃</i>	There is Long-run association between Quick ratio To debt to equity (DTE)	Accepted
<i>H₄</i>	There is Long-run association between Quick ratio To debt to assets (DTA)	Accepted
<i>H₅</i>	There is short-run association between current ratio to Debt to equity (DTE)	Rejected
<i>H₆</i>	There is short-run association between Current ratio to Debt To assets (DTA)	Accepted
<i>H₇</i>	There is short-run association between Quick ratio to Debt to Equity (DTE)	Rejected
<i>H₈</i>	There is short-run association between Quick ratio to Debt To assets (DTA)	Accepted
<i>H₉</i>	There is co-integration between variables.	Accepted

7. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Solvency & Liquidity are two very important aspects of profitability and firm performance of any business. The aim of this research was to investigate the short-run and long-run causality and association between dependent and independent variables using Vector Error correction model (VECM) by taking the case of Oil and Gas Development Company Limited (OGDCL), Pakistan. The research concluded that Current Ratio (CR) has no long-run association with Debt to Equity (DTE) and Debt to Assets (DTA), but Quick Ratio (QR) is having long-run association with Debt to Equity (DTE) and Debt to Assets (DTA). Moreover, Current Ratio (CR) has

short-run association with Debt to Assets (DTA). Similarly, Quick Ratio (QR) is having no short-run association with Debt to Equity (DTE), but having short-run association with Debt to Assets (DTA).

As extracted from results, OGDCL, Pakistan ought to concentrate on liquidity and solvency position in order to keep safe from any jeopardy in future because the results demonstrate that there is no long run association between current ratio and Debt to Equity and Debt to Assets. On some extent they have short run association and causality.

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